

A Study on Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed Students Teachers

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The attitude towards research basically means a detailed study of thinking, feeling and the person's behavior towards research. It is important to identify the attitudes towards research so that a positive attitude can be developed among students and hence their learning can be facilitated in turn.

In this work, the detail literature, analysis with data collected and the interpretation with its finding are discussed.

Review of Literature

Sadiashaukat, AishahSiddiquah, Muhammad Abiodullah & Rafaqat Data were analysed by using t-test and ANOVA. Results indicated that the males had significantly positive attitudes towards research than the females. Similarly significant results were found on age, different programs of study, and university type.

Intzar Hussain Butt & JahanAra Shams (2013) University of Education, Lahore conducted a study on 'Student Attitudes towards Research: A Comparison between two Public Sector Universities in Punjab': A significant difference was found in the attitudes with respect to the type of program and prior areas of specialization. The paper demonstrates a clear need for focus on research into student teacher attitudes towards research. Low student teacher attitudes have negative impact on the spread implications.

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the development of a new measure of attitude towards Educational Research for use among B.Ed. Student Teachers which operationalizes the affective attitudinal domain. Item selection, the internal structure and reliability of the scale, content validity and construct validity were established on a sample of 250 B.Ed. Student Teachers in the Educational Colleges in Coimbatore. A study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups that there is a significant with respect to medium of instruction and educational qualification and no significant with respect to gender, locality and marital status.

INTRODUCTION

Research plays a significant role in our daily life. All intentional have been possible with the help of research. With the help of research human being were able to find the cure for flue, polio and many other horrible diseases. Not only in medicine, had it also helped a lot in technology. Talking to long distance relatives is the outcome of research in technology. Research is the process of collecting and analyzing information to increase our understanding of the phenomenon. The aim of the research is to contribute towards the understanding to others. It gives rewarding learning experiences for students, producing graduates capable of high personal and professional achievement. Attitude is positive or negative affect towards a particular subject Dimensional definition of attitude includes emotions, beliefs, behaviors and their interaction.

Rwodzi Manuel, Rugaranganda Fenton and Manastsa Philemon (2013). The study recommends that the instructional process should be managed in appropriate ways, for example which provoke critical thinking in students, so as to create positive attitudes towards the quantitative research methods course which is numeric in nature.

Elena C. Papanastasiou (2012) conducted a study on the topic "Attitudes Toward Research". These were the factors of usefulness of research, anxiety, affect indicating positive feelings about research, life relevancy of research to the students' daily lives, and difficulty of research.

Kent G. Hecjer (2012) claimed that students with positive attitudes toward statistics in research are likely to show strong academic performance in statistics courses.

Allan Feldman & DilekOzalp (2012) conducted a study on 'Learning to do Research in a Research Experience for Undergraduates (REU) Program: In this Research Experiences for Undergraduates (REU) program. The paper includes implications for providing teachers with the knowledge and skills needed for them to teach their students how to engage in authentic scientific research practices.

Grant E. Gardner, Jennifer H. Forrester & Penny Shumaker Jeffrey (2012) The major findings demonstrated that

integration into a research community of practice revolved around students redefining the responsibilities of research scientists in the laboratory and negotiating the complex relationships in research settings.

Minjung Ryu & Tiffany-Rose Sikorski (2012) conducted a study on 'An Ethnographic Analysis of How Students' Perceived Identities Shape Science Classroom Discourse'. discuss the implication of these findings in terms of complexity science classroom discursive practices.

Objectives of the Study

To find out the significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed Student Teachers based on

- Gender : Male/Female
- Locality : Urban/Rural
- Marital Status : Married/unmarried
- Medium of instruction : Tamil/English
- Educational qualification : Educated/Uneducated

Research Questions

1. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers?
2. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers between the groups based on Gender?
3. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers between the groups based on Locality?
4. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers between the groups based on Marital Status?
5. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers between the groups based on Medium of instruction?
6. Is there any significant mean score difference in the in the attitude towards educational research among B.Ed. student teachers between the groups based on Educational qualification?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Gender.
2. There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Locality.
3. There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Marital Status.
4. There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Medium of instruction.
5. There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Educational Qualification.

Design of the Study

The research design is a plan of action, a plan of collecting and analyzing data in an economic, efficient and relevant manner. A research design could be constructed either to test a hypothesis or to give a cause-effect relationship to situation. Research design is a predetermined systematic outline that helps in explaining various concepts related to various subject for fulfilling particular objectives pertaining to the research study. The research design is not an ordered sequence of the steps followed for carrying a study rather it is the selection of the steps or components, keeping in view the objectives of the study which made logically visualizing practicability. Decisions regarding what, where, when, how much by what means constitute a research design. The investigator has selected Descriptive Survey Method for the Research.

Population of the Study

The population of the present study consists of B.Ed., Student Teachers studying in and around Coimbatore District. The sample for the present study will be 250 B.Ed., Student Teachers studying in and around Coimbatore District. The present study selected by simple Random Sampling Technique.

Tool Description

The "Personal Data Form" is used to collect the general information of the Student Teachers such as Name of the student, Name of the college, Gender, Religion, and Type of family, Medium of Instruction, Mother Tongue-curricular Activities, which was prepared by the investigator. Each statement consisted of three alternatives such as Agree, Not decided and Disagree.

Scoring of each item was done as shown in the table.

TABLE 1

Response	Score
Strongly Agree	SA
Agree	A
No opinion	N
Disagree	D
Strongly Disagree	SD

The independent sample t Test output also includes an approximate t statistic that is not based on assuming equal population variances; this alternative statistic, called the Welch t-Test statistic, may be used when equal variances among populations cannot be assumed. The Welch t Test is also known an Unequal Variance T Test or Separate Variance t-test.

It is calculated using the following formula,

$$t = \frac{\bar{X}_1 - \bar{X}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{S_2^2}{N_2}}}$$

Where,

N_1 & N_2 - Number of sample in each group.

\bar{X}_1 & \bar{X}_2 - Arithmetic mean of two group.

S_1 & S_2 - Standard deviation of two groups.

Analysis and interpretation of data

Hypotheses: 1 There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Gender.

TABLE 2 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Gender.

S. No	Gender	N	Mean	Df	T Value	P-value	Result
1	Male	97	2.9175	217	-0.3931	0.6946	S
2	Female	153	2.9869				

S → Significance
NS → Non Significance

The Table 2 shows the mean score difference in significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Gender. (Male/Female).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.69 levels and hence the hypotheses 1 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Gender.

CHART 1 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS GENDER AND THE LEVEL OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

Hypotheses: 2

There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Locality.

TABLE 3 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Locality.

S. No	Locality	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Urban	136	3.1324	246	-1.2534	0.2112	S
2	Rural	114	3.3509				

Interpretation

The Table 3 shows the mean score difference in significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Locality (Urban/Rural).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.21 levels and hence the hypotheses 2 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Locality.

CHART 2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS LOCALITY AND THE LEVEL OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

Hypotheses: 3

There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Marital Status.

TABLE 4 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Marital Status.

S. No	Marital Status	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Married	102	3.1078	218	1.2411	0.2159	S
2	Unmarried	148	2.8851				

The Table 4 shows the mean score difference in significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Marital Status (Married/Unmarried).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.21 levels and hence the hypotheses 3 is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Marital Status.

CHART 3 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS MARTIAL STATUS AND THE LEVEL OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

Hypotheses: 4

There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Medium of instruction.

TABLE 5 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Medium of Instruction.

S. No	Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Tamil	115	2.2353	231	-3.1962	0.0016	NS
2	English	135	2.8074				

The Table 5 shows the mean score difference in significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Medium of Instructions (Tamil/English).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.0016 levels and hence the hypotheses 4 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Medium of Instruction.

CHART 4 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION AND THE LEVEL OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

Hypotheses: 5

There is no significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Educational Qualification.

TABLE 6 Mean Score difference and t- value of factors related to significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Educational Qualification.

S. No	Educational Qualification	N	Mean	Df	t-Value	P-value	Result
1	Educated	198	2.2647	97	-3.9054	0.0002	NS
2	Uneducated	52	3.1538				

The Table 4.5 shows the mean score difference in significant study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Educational Qualification (Educated/Uneducated).The calculated t value is statistically high value, a significance at 0.05 to 0.0002 levels and hence the hypotheses 5 is rejected. It can be concluded that there is significant mean score difference in the level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups based on Educational Qualification.

CHART 9 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION AND THE LEVEL OF ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS

Summary of the Findings

A study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups that there is significant with respect to gender, locality and marital status. A study of level of Attitude towards Educational Research among B.Ed. Student Teachers between the groups that there is non significant with respect to medium of instruction and educational qualification.

Conclusion

The student-centered active learning process within which teacher is merely a guide is the focal point of contemporary education systems. The active learning is a learning process in which the learner takes the responsibility of his/her learning and s/he is given the opportunity to make decisions about various dimensions of the learning process and to perform self-regulation. In active learning process, learning is no longer a standard process, but it transforms into a personalized process. Here, the skills of problem-solving, critical thinking and learning to learn are developed. Humans face various problems in their lives and they try to find particular ways to solve these problems. In this respect, it is important for students to be prepared for the future by facing real or real-like problems in their learning environment and producing appropriate solutions to these problems. The basis of the problem-based learning is mainly comprised of 'Problem, Solution, Practice, Research, Questioning, Realism, Originality and Integration.' The aim of this learning model is to provide acquisition of information based on facts. In order to achieve this aim, problems are chosen out of the real world. The individual is being developed by making possible the integration with information accumulation of the student. Even though some differences are observed in practice, the problem-based learning is performed in sessions within which there are small working groups comprised of 6 or 8 persons guiding by an education mentor. They deal with scenarios involving several problems in above-mentioned sessions and try to find appropriate answers to these problems.

References

- [1] Ballard, M., & Pandya, M. (1990). Essential learnings in environmental education. Troy, OH: North American Association for Environmental Education.
- [2] Bögeholz, S. (2006). Nature experience and its importance for environmental knowledge, values and action: Recent German empirical contributions. *Environmental Education Research*, 12(1), 65-84.
- [3] Büyüköztürk, Ş. (2005). *Sosyal bilimler için veri analizi el kitabı [Handbook of data analysis for social sciences]* (5. Baskı). Ankara:
- [4] Cantekin Matbaası. Coyle, K. (2005). Environmental literacy in America: What ten years of NEETF/Roper research and related studies say about environmental literacy in the U.S. The National Environmental Education & Training Foundation. Retrieved September 30, 2018, from <http://www.neetf.org/pubs/ELR2005.pdf>.
- [5] Dietrich, H. (2013). The role of emotion in environmental decision making. Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. The Graduate College at the University of Nebraska, University of Nebraska, Lincoln,
- [6] Nebraska. Digby, B. L. C. (2010). An Examination of the Impact of Non-formal and Informal Learning on Adult Environmental Knowledge, Attitudes, and Behaviors. A Dissertation Submitted to the Faculty of the Graduate School of the University of Minnesota.
- [7] Dunlap, R. & Van Liere, K. (1978). The "new environmental paradigm." *The Journal of Environmental Education* 9(4), 10-19.
- [8] Dunlap, R. E., Van Liere, K. D., Mertig, A. G., & Jones, R. E. (2000). Measuring endorsement of the new ecological paradigm: A revised NEP scale. *Journal of Social Issues*, 56(3), 425-442.
- [9] Ewert, A., Place, G., & Sibthorp, J. (2005). Early-life outdoors experiences and individual's environmental attitudes. *Leisure Sciences*, 27, 225-239.
- [10] Flynn, B., Schroeder, R., & Sakakibara, S. (1994). A framework for quality management research and an associated measurement instrument. *Journal of Operations Management*, 11, 339-366. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0272-6963\(97\)90004-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0272-6963(97)90004-8).
- [11] Fraj-Andrés, Elena & Martínez-Salinas, Eva (2007). Impact of environmental knowledge on ecological consumer behavior: An empirical analysis. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, 19(3), 73-102.
- [12] Franzen, A. (2003). Environmental attitudes in international comparison: An analysis of the ISSP surveys 1993 and 2000*. *Social Science Quarterly* (Blackwell Publishing Limited), 84(2), 297-308.
- [13] Frick, J., Kaiser, F. G., & Wilson, M. (2004). Environmental knowledge and conservation behavior: Exploring prevalence and structure in a representative sample. *Personality & Individual Differences*, 37(8), 1597-1613.
- [14] Himmelfarb, S. (1993). The measurement of attitudes. In A. H. Eagly, & S. Chaiken (Eds.), *The psychology of attitudes*. Orlando, FL: Harcourt Brace Javanovich.
- [15] Hodgkinson, S. P., & Innes, J. M. (2001). The attitudinal influence of career orientation in 1st-year university students: Environmental attitudes as a function of degree choice. *Journal of Environmental Education*, 32(3), 37.
- [16] Holahan, C., J. (1982). *Environmental psychology*. 1st ed. Random House: New York. Kals, E., Schumacher, D. & Montada, L. (1999). Emotional affinity toward nature as a motivational basis to protect nature. *Environment & Behavior*, 31(2), 178-202.
- [17] Keles, O. (2011). Evaluation of primary school students' thought about and behaviors and attitudes towards

environment. Energy Education Science and Technology Part B: Social and Educational Studies,3(3): 343-358

[18] Knapp, D. (1996). Evaluating the impact of environmental interpretation: a review of three research studies. In Coalition for Education in the Outdoors Research Symposium Proceedings (Bradford, Woods, Indiana, January 12-14, 1996). (ERIC Document Reproduction Services No. ED413132).

[19] Krosnick, J. A., Judd, C. M., & Wittenbrink, B. (2005). The measurement of attitudes. In D. Albarracín, B. T. Johnson, & M. P. Zanna (Eds.), The handbook of attitudes (pp. 21–76). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum

[20] Leeming, F., Bracken, B., & Dwyer, W. (1995). Children's environmental attitude and knowledge scale: construction and validation. The Journal of Environmental Education, 26,22-33.

APPENDIX

PERSONAL DATA SHEET

- 1. Name :
- 2. Age :
- 3. Sex :
- 4. Locality :
- 5. Martial Status :
- 6. Educational qualifications :
- 7. Teaching Experience :
- 8. Internet Usage :
- 9. Kind of the college :

INSTRUCTION:

There are some statements below. Each statement is followed by multiple choices. (i.e) ‘Strongly agree,’ ‘Agree,’ ‘No opinion,’ ‘Disagree,’ ‘Strongly Disagree.’ Read each statement carefully. After reading each statement, mark your response in the appropriate columns by putting a tick mark. Feel free to respond to the questionnaire spontaneously without any hesitation. All the given statement are to be answered without any omission.

A STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH AMONG B.ED STUDENTS TEACHERS

S.NO	Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Innovations in the field of education is based on research					
2.	More funds should be allotted for educational research.					
3.	Teachers should be engaged and trained to do research in education.					
4.	Research is useful to every professional.					
5.	Research is a field that enhances the students interest.					
6.	I feel insecure concerning the analysis of research data.					
7.	Research should be taught to all students.					
8.	Research is useful for my career.					
9.	Research makes me anxious.					
10.	I enjoy while doing research work.					
11.	Research is connected to my field of study.					
12.	I make many mistakes in research.					
13.	I have trouble with statistics in research.					
14.	I am interested in research.					
15.	Most students benefit from research.					
16.	Research is stressful.					
17.	Research should be indispensable in my professional training.					
18.	Research is complicated.					
19.	Research thinking does not apply to my personal life.					
20.	Research makes me nervous.					
21.	I use research in my daily life.					
22.	Knowledge in research is useful for future innovations.					
23.	I am forced to study the details of research procedures carefully.					
24.	Action research is essential for an effective teacher.					
25.	Awareness about research should be provided to the students.					
26.	I will employ research approaches in my profession.					
27.	Research is very valuable.					
28.	Researchers are not adopting the ethics of research.					
29.	Research reviews form the basis for a research.					
30.	It is interesting to understand the various methods of research.					
31.	Research improves the creativity of the learner.					
32.	Research is systematic and scientific.					
33.	Research oriented thinking plays an important role in my daily life.					
34.	Research methodology is complicated.					
35.	I like research in the field of education.					